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Abstract

Art, especially in an Africa that was still smarting from the bewilderment of colonization by Europe, could not but be characterized by intentionality. Hence, beginning from Chinua Achebe’s seminal post-colonial and anti-imperialist novel *Things Fall Apart*, African writers devoted their artistry to disillusioning both Europe, on its false impressions of Africa, and Africans, on their mystified conception of the white man. According to Achebe himself, *Things Fall Apart* was written to make Europe understand that the African past “- with all its imperfections - was not one long night of savagery from which the first Europeans, acting on God's behalf, delivered them...” (*Morning...44*). This cardinal intention of freeing the people’s mind, as it were, is generally reflected in the plot, characterization, setting, language and thematic inclinations of the African writers’ works.